

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING MOTOR SKILLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN ENGLISH OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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The findings of the study suggest that improving fine motor skills can effectively promote communicative language learning, bring variety games and methods in the classrooms, motivate pupils to learn a foreign language, benefit the development of the fine motor skills in early age and vocabulary growth, supplement methods, and approach the curriculum topics via a different medium.

Fine motor skills can even be used as a predictor of school readiness or school performance. Achievement: For example, higher fine motor skills in preschool age are associated with higher one's kindergarten achievements in the areas of letter and word recognition, reading comprehension, vocabulary, phonological awareness, and mathematical performance¹ (Becker et al., 2014; Cameron et al., 2012; Sohn & Meisels, 2006). Several years later, this relationship still exists observed: Fine motor skills in preschool predict reading achievement in 2nd grade² (Dinehart & Manfra, 2013) and 3rd Class³ (McPhillips & Jordan-Black, 2007). Interestingly, some data suggest so a higher level of fine motor skills can be particularly beneficial for students who have difficulty with classrooms (eg., preschoolers with low to average English grades⁴ (Milne et al., 2018)) or for economically disadvantaged students⁵ (Dinehart & Manfra, 2013). Exactly these students, who have low fine motor skills early in kindergarten, are particularly at risk Difficulties not only in academic subjects but also in areas such as social and emotional adjusting to school and without intervention are at risk of falling behind their peers⁶ (Bart et al., 2007). A large proportion of children (10-24%) have fine motor skills difficulties, but fortunately meta-analytic evidence shows that interventions can be improved these skills are very successful⁷ (Strooband et a).

Early childhood is perhaps the most intense time for fine motor development skills including things like manipulating small objects, cutting with scissors, drawing, tracing and copying of figures⁸ (McHale & Cermak, 1992). Most of the time during days in the early childhood classrooms are spent on fine motor activities: studying, for example of 10 Head

¹ Becker et al., 2014; Cameron et al., 2012; Sohn & Meisels, 2006

² Dinehart & Manfra, 2013 Campos, J. J., Anderson, D. I., Barbu-Roth, M. A., Hubbard, E. M., Hertenstein, M. J., & Witherington, D. (2000). Travel broadens the mind. *Infancy*, 1, 149-219.

³ McPhillips & Jordan-Black, 2007 Autism spectrum disorders. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/data.html>.

⁴ Milne et al., 2018 Characterization of the neuropsychomotor development of children up to three years old: the ICF model in the context of the Family Health Support Center

⁵ Dinehart & Manfra, 2013 Persistent primary reflexes affect motor acts: Potential implications for autism spectrum disorder

⁶ Bart et al., 2007 The role of physical activity and body-related perceptions in motor skill competence of adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Disability and Rehabilitation*.

⁸ McHale & Cermak, 1992 *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 83, 287-295.

Start preschool and 10 kindergarten classrooms found that children, on average, in head Start spent between 27-46% and Kindergarteners between 36-66% school days for fine motor activities⁹ (Marr et al., 2003). Many kindergarten teachers' classrooms recognize the importance of developing these fine motor skills, which is why they integrate different activities throughout the school day to improve each of these four stages. For example: to cultivate whole arm skills, teachers can have students stir a large pot of dry noodles with a wooden stick. To cultivate whole-hand skills, students can use a sponge to transfer the water from one container to another. For pincher skills, teachers can teach students how to use them pliers and then ask them to pick up different items and sort them into groups. Finally to encourage pinch skills (those that require the greatest delicacy), teachers can show students how to use them keys for opening various types of locks¹⁰ (all examples adapted from Huffman & Fortenberry, 2011).

The child's physical growth and changes in muscle strength cause a great increase in the number of motor skills (Shaffer and Kipp, 2007). Many important motor skills gained in the first two years contribute to children's reaching better balance, speed, agility and power with increasing age (Feldman, 2004). Generally; Activities that move large muscle such as running, jumping, balancing, catching-throwing the ball, pulling-pushing objects attract the attention of children (Bukatko and Daehler, 2004). With each new motor skill, children gain new control over their bodies and their environment. These developments in the field of movement allow the child to access information about his/her environment and support their learning (Berk, 2013; Kail, 2004). Therefore, motor development; It develops in unity with the cognitive, language and social-emotional developments of the child (Boz and Güngör Aytar, 2012b; Kasten, 2017). From birth to 72 months, all aspects of motor development and other development areas should be evaluated and development should be supported (Temel et al., 2005). During this period, it is extremely important to support motor development.

After the birth, the cartilage continues to transform into bone and the bones lengthen and increase in number over time to form the skeletal structure that will support the body in its new physical adaptation. As the brain and nervous system mature, neural commands begin to coordinate the thickening and expanding muscles (Bee and Boyd, 2009; Bukatko and Daehler, 2004). In addition, the physical growth of babies requires that they learn to control their body movements (DeHart et al., 2004). This change in the physical structure and neuromuscular functions of the individual points to motor development (Rathus, 2008).

Motor skills are a system of motor reactions, abilities, skills and complex motor actions that are characteristic of a person. Fine motor skills - the development of small muscles of the fingers, the ability to perform fine coordinated manipulations with them¹¹. Motor skills (from the Latin word motor - setting in motion) - the motor activity of the body, its individual organs or parts¹². T. A. Vlasova, M. S. Pevzner (Т. А. Власова, М. С. Певзнер) define motor skills as a set of motor reactions, skills, abilities and complex motor actions inherent in a person.

By the term "fine motor skills" we mean highly differentiated precise movements of predominantly small amplitude and strength. Also, these are the exact movements of the

⁹ Marr et al., 2003 Disability and Rehabilitation.

¹⁰ Huffman & Fortenberry, 2011 Workshop on Assistive Technologies Emerging from Artificial Intelligence

¹¹ Мальцева, И. В. Совушка-сова, круглая голова / И. В. Мальцева. – М. : Карапуз, 2004. – 14 с.

¹² Бачина, О. В. Пальчиковая гимнастика с предметами. / О. В. Бачина. – М.: АРКТИ, 2009. – 88 с.

fingers and some elements of the articulatory apparatus. One of the components of motor abilities is fine motor skills¹³. Movement is a complex of

psychophysiological functions (processes) implemented by the body's motor apparatus.

Through movement, the internal organs of life support work, the body or its individual parts move in space, the posture and facial expressions change, the functional states of the body are regulated, and human labor activity is performed¹⁴.

Involuntary and voluntary movements are movements that a person distinguishes from each other in that some are performed unconsciously or automatically, while others are conscious and are performed with a goal planned by the individual.

Voluntary movements are formed based on involuntary movements because of the child's accumulation of motor experience and special training - the formation of motor skills and abilities. As children master the language, verbal regulation of movements appears.

A motor skill is an ability mastered to automatism to solve one or another type of motor task, based on a multi-level coordination structure formed in the process of learning, exercise and training¹⁵. Motor composition - a set of motor operations performed in a certain space-time mode in accordance with the content of the motor task and the external and internal means of its solution available to the subject. Motor sensations - sensations of the position of various parts of the body and its movements.

¹³ Никулина, А. А. Рисуем по точкам / А. А. Никулина. – М. : РОСМЭН–ПРЕСС, 2006. – 26 с.

References:

1. Becker et al., 2014; Cameron et al., 2012; Sohn & Meisels, 2006
2. Dinehart & Manfra, 2013 Campos, J. J., Anderson, D. I., Barbu-Roth, M. A., Hubbard, E. M., Hertenstein, M. J., & Witherington, D. (2000). Travel broadens the mind. *Infancy*, 1, 149-219.
3. McPhillips & Jordan-Black, 2007 Autism spectrum disorders. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/data.html>.
4. Milne et al., 2018 Characterization of the neuropsychomotor development of children up to three years old: the ICF model in the context of the Family Health Support Center
5. Dinehart & Manfra, 2013 Persistent primary reflexes affect motor acts: Potential implications for autism spectrum disorder
6. Bart et al., 2007 The role of physical activity and body-related perceptions in motor skill competence of adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Disability and Rehabilitation*
7. McHale & Cermak, 1992 *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 83, 287-295.
8. Marr et al., 2003 *Disability and Rehabilitation*.